

Facilitation Toolkit

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Keywords

Collaborative Problem-solving, Communication Studies, Cooperation, Educational Ethics, Facilitation, Frame Games, Gamification, Guided Discussion Techniques, Interactive Teaching, Method Cards, Teamwork, Workshop Design

Figure 1. Sample cards from the Facilitation Toolkit. Used for educational purposes. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The Facilitation Toolkit is a collection of method cards (see Figure 1) for educators and facilitators who lead game-based learning activities. The Game Didaktik Project at Leuphana University Lüneburg developed these cards because many instructors lack practical knowledge of facilitation techniques, even as interest in serious games and gamification is growing in higher education.

The cards are organized into five categories that reflect typical phases of facilitated learning sessions: icebreakers, knowledge activation, energizers, debriefing, and discussion formats. Each category has its own color and symbol for quick identification for users with color vision deficiency. The toolkit builds on the concept of frame games (Thiagarajan, 2004), reusable

activity structures that can be filled with different content depending on the learning context. Think-Pair-Share, for instance, keeps its structure whether applied to mathematical problems or ethical dilemmas.

The toolkit includes blank cards. Facilitators can add their own methods or invite workshop participants to contribute techniques from their practice. The collection grows with use.

Facts

Release date:	February 2026
Developer:	Saskia Sterzl, Leuphana University Lüneburg
Game type:	Analog (printed cards)
Number of players:	1–15
Format:	Standard playing card size (70 × 120 mm)
Time frame:	1.5–2 hours
Languages:	German
Environment:	Group table
Material:	Available as an Open Access download (PDF) on Zenodo and twillo; files are formatted for professional printing services or self-printing
Price:	Free (Open Access, CC-BY-SA)

Resonance & Criticism

The cards have been used in the "Mastering Facilitation" workshop developed by the Game Didaktik Project. Participant feedback from this workshop provides initial insights into how the toolkit functions in practice.

Participants particularly valued the playful approach and the practical outputs. One participant noted: "I left with concrete materials I can use immediately." The toolkit was described as versatile and immediately applicable. Systematic follow-up data on independent use is not yet available.

Game Principle & Process

Each card follows a consistent structure for quick orientation. The front shows the method name, goal, and required preparation or materials. The back outlines the procedure and includes practical tips.

The five categories cover different moments in facilitated sessions. Icebreakers help establish a supportive learning environment and reduce initial nervousness. Knowledge activation methods help participants recall and connect prior knowledge before engaging with new content. Energizers wake up the group physically and mentally, particularly useful after periods of concentrated work. Discussion formats give participants a clear structure for exchange and debriefing techniques that structure reflection after learning activities.

Methods range from well-established classics like World Café and Think-Pair-Share to creative approaches such as “Montagsmaler” (a drawing-based review game) and "Love Letters" for peer feedback. Some methods require no preparation, while others require specific materials; the cards clearly indicate these requirements.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The toolkit is designed for educators and facilitators who want to expand their method repertoire. It is suitable for preparing courses, workshops, or training: the cards can be browsed by category to find appropriate methods for specific phases. The blank cards invite users to add their own methods. Browsing the full collection takes approximately one hour; selecting methods for a specific session typically requires five to fifteen minutes.

An application example: In the "Mastering Facilitation" workshop of the Game Didaktik Project, the toolkit serves as both teaching material and takeaway resource. Participants receive a printed copy at the end to take into their own practice.

Effectiveness

Formal evaluation studies are not yet available. Frame games have been used in training contexts for decades (Thiagarajan, 2004), and skilled facilitation is critical to learning outcomes in game-based learning (Crookall, 2010). One workshop participant reported that handling the cards helped them remember the methods better and made it more likely to use them, compared with digital bookmarks or PDF documents.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

As with any collection method, there is a risk that users treat the cards as recipes to follow mechanically rather than as frameworks to adapt. The brief card format necessarily simplifies methods that often have considerable depth and variation. Facilitators new to game-based learning may benefit from additional training or mentorship in addition to the toolkit.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

Crookall, D. (2010). Serious games, debriefing, and simulation/gaming as a discipline. *Simulation & Gaming*, 41(6), 898-920. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878110390784>

Thiagarajan, S. (2004). Thiagi's interactive lectures: Power up your training with interactive games and exercises. ASTD Press.